

Cell Electrical Properties: Combustion of water

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

It's important to understand that the water of the cell isn't water. It's a gel-phase of water that retains hydroxide ions and excludes hydrogen ions, H_3O_2^- , not H_2O . *The cell is not composed of H_2O , it's composed of H_3O_2^- .* This cell-water is therefore in reduced form, it is an oxide with a surplus of electrons. This gel is the anode of the base electrical potential of the cell, the resting potential. The cell converts water into a negative pole, it charges the water. The cell is a battery that runs on water.

The cell is organized on the ability of water to form a "gel-phase", analogous to ice that has excluded the hydrogen ions that bind the ice lattice sheets together vertically. The entire cell can be modelled as a single gel-phase blob, polarized, multilayered water organized around the cell protein matrix as scaffold. This gel-phase excludes hydrogen ions, causing the -100 mV negative charge of the cell (Pollack, 2014).

The cell is able to use water as an energy source because the cell protein matrix is a scaffold that organizes H_2O into H_3O_2^- . This basic organizational structure of the cell inherently "tears water apart". The cell in the resting state is already halfway through the chemical process of water catalysis, it has isolated the gel-phase H_3O_2^- by excluding H^+ from the cell. Collapsing the gel-phase — depolarization — lets the second half of the reaction take place, $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4\text{e}^-$.

This is what releases electrical energy as the cell depolarizes. The energy necessary to pay for this reaction is ATP that structures the water-splitting complex that is the cell protoplasm, and, chemical energy in electrolytes like potassium and sodium that stabilize the water-splitting cell (Ling, 1952, 1965; Nasonov, 1962), and, radiant energy that splits the water into the gel-phase that permeates the cell (Pollack, 2014).

References

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